
Introduction

Flood risk assessment is an important and complex task requiring various data sources and multi-factor analysis. Many studies have considered various factors in flood risk assessment, i.e. physical as well as socio-economic factors and preventive actions (Efraimidou and Spiliotis, 2024). The following instructions focus on the potential harm due to geographical and meteorological factors, often described as *flood hazard* (Tsakiris, 2007). In this short introduction to flood hazard mapping, we only make use of a small number of data sources to allow application in cases where sufficient data is lacking.

Data & software requirements

Required data

Various physical factors must be analyzed in any flood risk assessment. The potential flood hazard will largely be derived from topographic features and other characteristics of local terrain such as *Land Use*, *Elevation*, *Slope*, *Proximity to Streams* and amount of *Precipitation*. These can be drawn from basic datasets of *Land Cover Classification (LC)*, *Digital Elevation Model (DEM)* and *Annual Precipitation*. Further information on data sources is found in the appendix.

Required software

Spatial data can be processed in a Geographic Information System (GIS) such as the standard (licensed) *ArcGIS Pro Software* from ESRI or the open-source *QGIS*. These tools provide the necessary applications to read certain data types and implement functions such as the processing and workflow analysis of raster- and vector data.

Preprocessing data: deriving potential flood hazard factors from datasets

Before performing the hazard assessment, the influencing factors described above must be derived from the datasets of classification data, DEM and precipitation. *Land Use* can be determined from *LC-Data*, which is available in processed form or can be derived from remote-sensing data. The creation of land cover classification is a complicated topic in its own right, which will not be discussed further here. There are many online and printed resources on how to perform easy but useful classifications from scratch. *Annual Precipitation* data can also be found online from various sources. Here it makes sense to calculate an annual or monthly mean of time intervals with high precipitation to determine areas that are most affected by strong rainfall. Influential terrain factors can be derived from a *DEM* (compare Fig. 1). Before any further processing, land sinks should be filled to provide a steady downhill gradient in the dataset. Subsequently *Flow Direction* and from this *Flow Accumulation* can be calculated to reveal the pixels with the highest flow concentration. To determine the *Distance* or *Proximity to Streams*, the main stream channels have to be extracted by reclassifying the *Flow Accumulation* layer; this is achieved by setting a threshold of 1% of the maximum accumulation-value and assigning no-data to all other values. The stream proximity is given by the Euclidean distance to the new main stream layer. The missing *Slope* factor is provided by the *DEM* dataset. GIS Software offers the functions and necessary instructions for the individual processing steps. The spatial resolution of the final flood risk

map is determined by the dataset with the lowest resolution, which will usually be precipitation or soil data.

Fig. 1: Workflow to calculate Proximity to Streams from DEM

Multi-criteria assessment of potential flood hazard

There are various methods to assess a multi-factor flood hazard. One simple technique for a multi-criteria analysis is to calculate a weighted sum. Before combining all factors into a final hazard score, the various datasets (which may apply different units) must be converted into a neutral scale by reclassification, e.g. into five ranks of potential flood risk ranging from very low to very high (see Table 1). While numerical data can be automatically assigned a risk ranking, it is important to consider the scaling order for each factor. For example, while the potential flood hazard from precipitation increases with higher rainfall, it decreases with higher slope values because of the downward flow direction in the landscape. Non-numerical data such as land cover or soil type must be reclassified in a way that reflects their relationship to flood risk. Developed areas may have structures that lower flood risk while agricultural areas and wetlands are more susceptible to flood events.

Table 1: Risk score assigned to all datasets to produce a ranking

Value	Risk intensity
2	very low
4	low
6	medium
8	high
10	very high

Table 2: Example of reclassifying land use to hazard score, depending on degree of protection against flood events

Influential Factor	Weight [%]
Elevation (DEM)	10
Slope	15
Land Use	10
Precipitation	35
Proximity to Streams	30

Subsequently, all reclassified layers are combined in a weighted sum to calculate a final flood hazard score. The individual weights (Table 2) are determined by each factor's impact on flooding. The resulting image layer (Fig. 2) shows the summed flood hazard for each pixel in the investigated area. To improve readability, the resulting image values can be reclassified into a smaller ranking table based on the scale applied to all datasets (compare "risk intensity" in Table 1).

Potential Flood Hazard for Huangyan-Taizhou, China

Fig. 2: resulting flood risk map from final hazard score

Literature on flood risk assessment

Efracimidou, E., Spiliotis, M., 2024. A GIS-Based Flood Risk Assessment Using the Decision-Making Trial and Evaluation Laboratory Approach at a Regional Scale. *Environ. Process.* 11, 9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40710-024-00683-w>

Tsakiris, G., 2007. Practical Application of Risk and Hazard Concepts in Proactive Planning. *European Water* 19/20, 47–56.

Data sources for environmental data

- **USGS-Earth Explorer**
30m Satellite Imagery, Land Cover, Elevation Data (DEM)
<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>
- **Copernicus Browser**
10m Satellite Imagery
<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>
- **ESRI Land Cover from Living Atlas of the World**
10m Land Cover Data
<https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=cfc7609de5f478eb7666240902d4d3d>
- **WorldClim**
Historical Climate Data (1970-2000)
<https://www.worldclim.org/data/worldclim21.html>
- **Copernicus Climate**
European Climate Data
<https://climate.copernicus.eu/esotc/2021/about-data#ERA5>

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The project on which this technical instruction is based was funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research under funding number 01LE1804B1. Responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors.

Funded by:

Das dieser Technischen Anleitung zugrunde liegende Vorhaben wurde mit Mitteln des Bundesministeriums für Bildung und Forschung unter dem Förderkennzeichen 01LE1804B1 gefördert. Die Verantwortung für den Inhalt dieser Veröffentlichung liegt bei der Autorin/ beim Autor.

